

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN INTENTION TO LEAVE AND PERSON ORGANIZATION FIT OF GYMNASTICS COACHES

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Abstract:

In this research, the relationship between intention to leave and person organization fit is studied via determining of some variables. For data collection, Scale of Intentions to Leave developed by Rosin and Korabik (1995) and Person Organization Fit Scale developed by Netemeyer et al (1997) is utilized in the relational screening model research on 181 gymnastics coaches. Results have shown that coaches' intentions to leave are low and variables such as branch, gender, marital status and level of income have no meaningful effect. Participants' average scores are found to be high and level of person organization fit displays a meaningful difference in relation with level of income. In regards with results within correlations, there is a negative and mid-level relationship between intentions to leave and person organization fit levels of coaches in men/women artistic gymnastics.

Keywords: gymnastics, coaches, person organization fit, intention to leave

1. Introduction

In recent years, scholars in the field of organizational behavior and human resource management have shown great interest in the concept of Person-Environment (P-E) fit. P-E is a broad concept which includes the harmony of an employee with many systems in the work environment. The concept of (P-E) fit includes Person-Vocation (P-V) fit, Person-Organization (P-O) fit, Person-Job (P-J) fit and Person-Group (P-G) fit (Morley, 2007: 109, Kristof, 1996).

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The concept of person-organization fit is evaluated as a type of person-environment fit. The simplest definition of “person-organization fit” is the compatibility level between persons and organizations. However, in order to establish this compatibility to its full extent, there must be a harmony between the person and the organization in many sub-dimensions. Looking at previous studies conducted on this field, there are certain criteria for complete establishment of person-organization harmony. These criteria are, respectively, the harmony between the requirements of work and the talent, ability, skills and knowledge of employee; the harmony between the culture and values of the person and of the organization; and the harmony between the character of employee and the environment of organization (Kristof, 1996, Morley, 2007: 110).

The concept of “person-organization fit” has a significant place among organizational behavior, industrial psychology and human resources disciplines. Nonetheless, person-organization fit brings along many other important results in terms of attitude towards work, inter-personal dynamics and behaviors. What is especially underlined in person-organization fit is that the values of person must match an organizational value system and this match (or mismatch) is one of the most prominent factors contributing to the attitude of person within the organization (Behram ve Dinç, 2014).

In this context, high level of person-organization fit brings along positive results which might transform into long term benefits for the organization. Low level of person-organization fit might cause many negative results both for the person and the organization (Kristof, 1996).

One of the most prominent among these negative results is the intention of leaving the job. The intention of leaving the job, which significantly decreases the employee performance, also causes abnormal behavior such as slowdown and sabotage. Intention of leaving the job generally results with the action of leaving the job and this has a significant cost for the company (Behram ve Dinç, 2014).

Studies conducted on this field suggests that person-organization fit positively affects many factors including job satisfaction, loyalty to organization, stress perception, group activity perception, personnel transfer and rate of turnover intention. On the other hand, person-organization fit, which increase support and trust between employees and reduce ambiguity and facilitate better communication, also has positive effects on employees. (Cable and Edwards, 2004; Giberson vd., 2005). In addition, a study conducted by Ng and Sarris (2009) on person-organization fit, it has been understood that participants who have a low level of person-organization fit also have low level of

organizational loyalty and participants with high level of person-organization fit have high level of job satisfaction.

In addition, it has been understood that there is a correlation between person-organization fit and turnover intention. According to these results, it is suggested that an increment in person-organization fit decreases the rate of turnover intention (Chatman, 1991; O'Reilly vd., 1991; Kristof, 1996; McCulloch and Turban, 2007; Wheeler vd., 2007; Behram and Dinç, 2014).

Employee turnover intentions have negative influence on organizational performance since employees are the most valuable asset for an organization; managers always try to identify the factors causing turnover intention in their organization. Based on this, the purpose of this study is to determine the level of person-organization fit and rate of turnover intention for coaches.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Person-Organization-Fit

Person-organization fit has a significant place in organizational behavior. Person-organization fit is one of the sub-dimensions of person-environment fit, which is a broader concept. (Morley, 2007: 109). Person-organization fit studies, which started after Tom's (1971) suggestion that employees would work better in organizations which fit their character traits, today is built mainly on Schneider's Attraction-Selection-Attrition model proposed in 1987.

Schneider's ASA model proposed in his study dated 1987 defines the reciprocal harmony mechanism between the person and the organization under three different dimensions. Attraction dimension suggests that the person will define the organization more attractive if the structure, culture and values of the organization is more harmonious with his personal preferences, character and values. In terms of selection dimension, organizations will have an inclination to select individuals who have similar characteristics and values to their own. Attrition dimension stands for an individual leaving the organization due to an incompatibility between the individual and the organization. (Parkes vd, 2001, Morley, 2007: 110, Cable and Judge 1996). ASA model defines how persons and organizations are attracted to each other. (Wheeler et al. 2013:207). According to this model, characteristics of people and characteristics of the organization they fit in have variety and people tend to work at organizations which have traits fitting the values, needs and personality of them. (Yıldız, 2013:156).

Kristof (1996) evaluated person-organization fit from a broad perspective and defined it as the harmony which emerges from a) at least one of the parties providing

the needs of the other, b) parties sharing similar fundamental traits and c) both of these options.

The term “person -organization (PO) fit” has been used to describe the congruence between individual and organizational goals; individual preferences or needs and organizational systems or structures; and individual personality and organizational climate (Kristof, 1996).

Studies conducted on relevant researchers (Chatman, 1991; Cable ve Judge, 1996; Kristof-Brown vd., 2005) has proven that person-organization fit positively affect many attitudinal approaches towards work such as job satisfaction, organizational loyalty, perceived stress and decreased turnover intention. In this context, high level of person-organization fit brings along positive results which might transform into long term benefits for the company while low level of person-organization fit might have many negative results both for the employee and for the organization (Behram and Dinç, 2014).

2.2 Turnover Intentions

Employees establish a turnover intention before leaving their workplace. This intention, which translates as a conscious and cautious decision to leave the job (Barlett, 1999: 70), is defined as “turnover intention” in literature.

Turnover *Intention* has become a major concern for management in this century because organizations make huge investments on their employees in terms of recruiting, training, developing and retaining them. Turnover intention can be defined as the intention of an employee to quit his current job and discarding of his or her organizational membership (Meyer & Allen, 1984). In another saying, turnover intention is “*the individual calculation made by employees on the possibility of a future turnover.*” (Vandenberg and Nelson, 1999). Mobley, on the other hand, defined turnover intention as “*the intention or the thought of an employee to leave the job in near future*” in 1982 (Mobley, 1982).

Determining the factors that contribute to turnover has a great deal of importance in terms of taking certain precautions to foresee the action of turnover and to prevent potential turnovers Loi, R., Hang-Yue, N., & Foley, S., 2006; Mayfield and Mayfield, 2008).

As it is clearly underlined in the literature the importance of valuable and skillful employees in an organization’s success and also that less those employees think of leaving their job, higher their performance and increased organizational productivity (Loi, R., Hang-Yue, N., & Foley, S., 2006; Mayfield and Mayfield, 2008; Tolukan, Bayrak and Karacan Dogan, 2017). Turnovers have significant negative effects such as loss of

qualified workforce, new selection and placement efforts, internal service training of the replacement, productivity loss during adaptation process of the replacement, loss of investment spent on the previous employee, new investments that will be spent on the replacement, duration of adaptation to work, loss of high performance, disturbance in social and communication structures within the organization. (Kuean vd., 2010, Bibby, 2008; Scott vd., 1999).

On the other hand, even if not resulting with the action of turnover, turnover intention alone has lots of significant effects on the organization. In addition, Bowen proved in his 1982 study that turnover intention has a set of negative effects such as absence and low performance. Similarly, Mowday vd. (1982) proposed that in case an individual maintains his position in the organization despite having turnover intention; he would display his dissatisfaction by certain ways such as sabotage, absence and slowdown, which would damage the organization.(Referenced by: Behram ve Dinç, 2014).

3. Method

This section includes the model, universe, sampling, data collection tools and data analyses of the research.

3.1 Method of the Research

This research aims to analyse the correlation between person-organization fit and turnover intention of men's and women's artistic gymnastics coaches. This research is an example of relational screening model. Under the scope of this research, it is also evaluated whether turnover intention and person-organization fit level of coaches differ significantly based on gender, marital status, branch, degree major and monthly income. Demographic features of participants were determined to be independent variables whereas turnover intention and person-organization fit level were determined to be dependent variables.

3.2 Sample and Universe

Universe of this research comprises of 210 people in total, 85 of which are men's artistic gymnastics coaches whereas 125 of which are women's artistic gymnastics coaches. Sample of this research comprises of 181 people in total, 82 of which are men's artistic gymnastics coaches and 99 of which are women's artistic gymnastics coaches.

3.3 Data Collection Tools

Data collected under the scope of this study are gathered from Personal Information Form, Turnover Intention Scale and Person-Organization Fit Scale.

3.4 Turnover Intention Scale

In order to determine the turnover intention of coaches, Turnover Intention Scale (0,930), which was developed by Rosin and Korabick (1995) and adapted to the Turkish language, by Tanrıöver (2005), is used in this research. High scores indicate high level of turnover intention whereas low scores correspond to low level of turnover intention.

In this research, Cronbach alpha reliability multiplier, which is based on the answers provided by 181 coaches to turnover intention scale questions, is measured to be 0,858. In another saying, reliability of answers provided to the intention scale questions is high. (Kalaycı, 2009) In order to determine whether coaches participated in the research evaluated the scale questions under a single dimension just like the original version, exploratory factor analysis is conducted at the same time. As a result of exploratory factor analysis, it has been understood that there is a single factor with eigenvalue higher than 1, and items of the scales illicit %71,660 of total variance. It has been also understood that factor load value of the questions are 0,906; 0,913; 0,878 and 0,663 respectively. In another saying, it has been understood that the dimension of scale questions much clearly define a single dimension. RMSEA=0,041; CFI=0,99; NFI=0,99; GFI= 0,97 values of fit indexes measured in order to test the reliability of the scale also indicate that model-data harmony is achieved. It is understood that coaches participating in this research provided valid and reliable answers to the questions listed in turnover intention scale.

3.5 Person Organization Fit Scale

Person-organization fit scale developed by Netemayer et al (1997) was used in order to determine person-organization fit level of coaches participated in this research. Scale consists of four items and those items were graded using Likert type 5 point scale. It has been understood that Cronbach alpha internal consistency reliability multiplier is 0,88. A study conducted by Turunç and Çelik (2012) measured the reliability of responses provided to scale items as 0,81. Under the scope of this research, in order to determine the reliability of the responses of men's artistic gymnastics coaches and women's artistic gymnastics coaches provided to person-organization fit scale items, Cronbach alpha internal consistency reliability multiplier is measured and it is 0,896. Following the exploratory factor analysis, it has been understood that there was a single dimension which has an eigenvalue higher than 1. It has been also understood that items of the

scales illicit %71,660 of total variance. Factor loads of the items were measured to be 0,861; 0,910; 0,930 and 0,801 respectively. In addition, confirmatory factor analysis is also conducted in order to determine whether responses provided by coaches validated the research model.

Fit indexes measured to test model-data compatibility is as follows: RMSEA= 0,080; CFI= 1,00; NFI= 0,99; GFI= 0,99. Measured values suggest that model-data compatibility is excellent.

3.6 Data Analysis

First, descriptive statistics of data collected in this research is identified (number of people, minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation etc.). Then, data analysis is conducted based on the problems cited in this research. In order to determine whether person-organization fit and turnover intention of coaches have a significant correlation; t test, one-way variance analysis (ANOVA), multiple comparison LSD test and Kruskall Wallis test is used in independent measurements. Pearson correlation multiplier is measured in order to determine the correlation between person-organization fit and turnover intention. Significance level of difference tests are 0,05 by standard.

Kurtosis skewness multiplier is used to determine the distribution of data sets collected from coaches. It has been understood that person-organization fit scale multipliers are -0,821; 0,013; turnover intention scale multipliers are 0,731 and -0,296. In another saying, it has been understood that standard deviation is between -1 and +1 which translates to no abnormality.

4. Findings

In this section, there are findings through the sub-problems included in the research.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics on turnover intention of coaches

Scale	Number of Factors	N	Lowest	Highest	SS
turnover intention	4	181	4,00	20,00	8,80 4,54

Analysing the data displayed on the Table 1 it has been understood that turnover intention points of coaches, whose opinion were collected, ranged between 4.00 to 20.00. Point average of responses provided is 8,80. In another saying, it has been understood that turnover intention of men's artistic gymnastics coaches and women's artistic gymnastics coaches remained below 44%.

Table 2: T test results of branch oriented turnover intentions of coaches based using independent measurement

Scale	Branch	N	SS	t	p	
Turnover intention	Men's artistic gymnastics	82	9,23	4,98	1,162	0,247
	Women's artistic gymnastics	99	8,44	4,14		

Analysing the data provided on the Table, it has been understood that turnover intention of coaches did not differ significantly based on their branches ($t_{(179)}=1,162$; $p>0,05$). In another saying, turnover intention of Men's artistic gymnastics coaches ($=9,23\pm4,98$) and turnover intention of Women's artistic gymnastics coaches ($=8,44\pm4,14$) were similar.

Table 3: T test results of gender oriented turnover intentions of coaches based on independent measurement

Scale	Gender	N	SS	t	p	
Turnover intention	Female	67	8,31	4,15	1,108	0,269
	Male	114	9,09	4,75		

Analysing the data provided on the Table, it has been understood that turnover intention of coaches did not differ significantly based on their genders ($t_{(179)}=1,108$; $p>0,05$). In another saying, turnover intention of Male artistic gymnastics coaches ($=9,09\pm4,75$) and turnover intention of Female artistic gymnastics coaches ($=8,31\pm4,15$) were similar.

Table 4: T test results of marital status oriented turnover intentions of coaches based on independent measurement

Scale	Marital status	N	SS	t	p	
Turnover intention	Married	86	8,83	4,61	0,069	0,945
	Single	95	8,78	4,50		

Analysing the data provided on the Table, it has been understood that turnover intention of coaches did not differ significantly based on their marital status ($t_{(179)}=0,069$; $p>0,05$). In another saying, turnover intention of married artistic gymnastics coaches ($=8,83\pm4,61$) and turnover intention of single artistic gymnastics coaches ($=8,78\pm4,50$) were similar.

It is aimed to detect whether turnover intentions of gymnastics coaches differ in a significant manner based on the department that they are graduated from or not. For detection of this; It is tested with Levene test that whether the variances are homogenous or not and it is founded that the variances are not homogenous (Levene 4,774; $p < 0,05$). Kruskal Wallis test had been conducted for determining whether the turnover intentions of gymnastics coaches differ based on the department they are graduated from and the results shown in the Table below.

Table 5: Kruskal Wallis test results that stands for the relation between the department they are graduate from and turnover intentions of gymnastics coaches

Scale	Degree	N	Mean Rank	sd	p
Turnover Intention	Sports Academy	138	94,79	2	4,987
	Academy Other Than Sports	20	90,38		
	No Degree	23	68,83		

Analysing the data provided on the Table, it has been understood that turnover intention of coaches did not differ significantly based on the degree they are holding ($F_{(2)}=4,987$; $p > 0,05$). In another saying, turnover intention of artistic gymnastics coaches that are holding a degree of Sports Academy ($=9,11 \pm 4,56$), turnover intention of artistic gymnastics coaches that are holding a degree of an Academy Other Than Sport ($=9,10 \pm 5,39$) and turnover intention of artistic gymnastics coaches that has no degree ($6,70 \pm 2,95$) were similar.

Table 6: One way ANOVA results that is calculated for determining whether the turnover intentions of artistic gymnastics coaches differs based on their monthly income or not

Scale	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	sd	Mean of Squares	F	p
Turnover Intention	Intergroup	103,281	2	51,641	2,548	,081
	Intragroup	3607,559	178	20,267		
	Sum	3710,840	180			

Analysing the data provided on the Table, it has been understood that turnover intention of coaches did not differ significantly based on their monthly incomes ($F_{(2, 180)}=2,548$; $p > 0,05$). In another saying turnover intention of artistic gymnastics coaches that has a monthly income below the average ($=9,15 \pm 4,49$), turnover intention of artistic gymnastics coaches that has a monthly income on average level ($9,11 \pm 4,62$) and

turnover intention of artistic gymnastics coaches that have a monthly income above the average ($=7,04\pm4,00$) were similar.

Table 7: Descriptive statistics that has been calculated related with the person-organization fit level of coaches

Scale	Number of articles	N	Minimum	Maximum	SS
Person-organization fit level	4	181	4,00	20,00	15,73 3,94

Analysing the data provided on the Table, it has been understood that the lowest score of the coaches on articles created for calculating person-organization fit level is 4,00 and highest score of the coaches on articles created for calculating person-organization fit level is 20,00. The coaches has a 15,73 average of person-organization fit level. In another saying person-organization fit levels of the coaches that are participating on this study is above average and in the level of 79%.

Table 8: T test results that has been calculated for determining the relationship between person-organization fit level and branch of coaches

Scale	Branch	N	SS	t	p
Person-organization fit level	Male Artistic gymnastics	82	15,98	4,19	0,748 0,455
	Female Artistic gymnastics	99	15,54	3,72	

Analysing the data provided on the Table, it has been understood that person-organization fit level of coaches did not differ significantly based on their branch ($t_{(179)}=0,748$; $p>0,05$). In another saying, person-organization fit level of artistic gymnastics coaches of males ($=15,98\pm4,19$) person-organization fit level of artistic gymnastics coaches of females($=15,54\pm3,72$) were similar.

Table 9: T test results that has been calculated for determining the relationship between person-organization fit level and genders of coaches

Scale	Gender	N	SS	t	p
Person-organization fit level	Female	67	15,58	3,52	0,399 0,690
	Male	114	15,82	4,17	

Analysing the data provided on the Table, it has been understood that turnover intention of coaches did not differ significantly based on their genders ($t_{(179)}=0,399$;

$p > 0,05$). In another saying, person-organization fit level of female coaches ($15,58 \pm 3,52$) and person-organization fit level of male coaches ($=15,82 \pm 4,17$) were similar.

Table 10: T test results that has been calculated for determining the relationship between person-organization fit level and marital status of coaches

Scale	Marital Status	N	SS	t	p
Person-organization fit level	Married	86	15,94	3,98	0,673
	Single	95	15,55	3,90	

Analysing the data provided on the Table, it has been understood that turnover intention of coaches did not differ significantly based on their marital status ($t_{(179)} = 0,673$; $p > 0,05$). In another saying, person-organization fit level of married coaches ($15,94 \pm 3,98$) and person-organization fit level of single coaches ($=15,55 \pm 3,90$) were similar.

Variances of person-organization fit level and the Degree they hold tested with the Levene test and it is seen that coaches within the scope of this study do not have a homogenous variance of these variables. (Levene 5,019; $p < 0,05$). Kruskal Wallis test statistics had been calculated for determining whether the person-organization fit level shows a significant difference based on the Degree coaches holding and the results are shown in the Table.

Table 11: Kruskal Wallis test results of person-organization fit levels of coaches based on their degrees

Scale	Degree	N	Average	sd	p
Person-organization fit	Sports academy	138	90,91	2	2,272
	Academy other than sports	20	78,53		
	No degree	23	102,37		

Analysing the data provided on the Table, it has been understood that person-organization fit of coaches did not differ significantly based on their degree ($\chi^2_{(2)} = 2,272$; $p > 0,05$). In another saying, person-organization fit level of coaches that are graduated from Sports Academy ($15,78 \pm 3,84$), coaches that are graduated from an Academy other than sports ($=14,30 \pm 5,15$) and coaches not holding a degree ($=16,74 \pm 2,99$) were similar.

Table 12: One way ANOVA results that is calculated for determining whether the turnover intentions of artistic gymnastics coaches differ based on their monthly income or not

Scale	Source of variance	Sum of squares	sd	Mean of squares	F	p
Person-organization fit level	Inter-groups	146,297	2	73,149	4,930	,008
	Group (internal)	2640,974	178	14,837		
	Total	2787,271	180			

Analysing the table above, it has been understood that monthly income of coaches significantly contribute to person-organization fit ($F_{(2,180)}=4,930$; $p>0,05$). Multiple comparative LSD test is used to determine in which groups there are difference. Results of LSD test suggests that person-organization fit level of coaches who have a higher monthly income ($=17,82\pm3,60$) are higher when compared to coaches with lower than average monthly income ($=15,15\pm3,54$) and coaches with average monthly income ($=15,42\pm4,01$).

Table 13: Correlation between turnover intention and person-organization fit level of coaches

Variable	Values	Person-organization fit	Intention of leaving the job
Person-organization fit	r	1	-,585**
	p		,000
	N	181	181

Following the analysis of information listed in the Table, it has been understood that there is negative and mediocre level of correlation between turnover intentions and person-organization fit levels of men's artistic gymnastics coaches and women's artistic gymnastics ($r=-0,585$; $p<0,05$). In another saying, it is understood that as turnover intentions of coaches increase, their person-organization fit level decrease and as turnover intentions decrease, their person-organization fit level increase.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

As a result, based on collected data it was determined that turnover intention of gymnastics coaches was under the average (around 44%). According to these results, it could be said that the coaches were generally pleased with their jobs and their workplaces.

In the gymnastics sport, the branches of man gymnastics and woman gymnastics are regarded as two separate branches. In this direction, when turnover intentions of the coaches that were involved in our exemplification according to their branches were analyzed, it was determined that they revealed no significant variance. ($t_{(179)}=1,162$; $p>0,05$) Oja et al., in the study which they had realized with 867 coaches in the year of 2015, who were taking charge of the structure of the NCAA (National Collegiate Athletics Association), determined that the coaches that were working with woman teams revealed lower intention to leave job compared to the coaches that were working with man teams (Oja, Schaeperkoetter and Clopton, 2015).

As the result of the analysis that was made, no variance was encountered among the intentions to leave job as per the variants such as the coaches' gender, marital status, the department that they had been graduated and monthly income. When the studies which had investigated the effects of the demographic variants on the intention of leaving job were examined, no meaningful difference was found between the women and men with regard to their intentions to leave job were examined, in the study Uysal-Irak (2014) made with 283 participants concerning the gender variant, no meaningful difference was found between women and men with regard to their intentions of leaving job. (Uysal-Irak, 2014) But, Turesin (2012), in a study which he had made about public institutions, determined that the intentions of woman workers to leave job were higher compared to the man workers (Turesin, 2012: 151).

As to the independent variant of the marital status, Turesin, in his study which he had made in the year of 2012, reached the solution of the intentions of the married ones for job and to leave job were higher compared to the single ones. Oja et al., in the study which they made in the year of 2015, determined that the cases of the NCAA coaches' being paid low prices increased the intentions of leaving job, as well. The person-organization fits of the coaches, whose opinions were taken into the scope of the research, were determined to be at the level of 79%. This high fit level may be interpreted as the coaches' devotion to their branches and their making sport's contributing to their compliance to their jobs and business places.

As the result of the analyses conducted in our study, it was determined that the person-organization fit level of Men's Artistic Gymnastics branch coaches were higher when compared to Women's Artistic Gymnastics branch coaches and fit levels of married coaches were higher when compared to single coaches and also that fit level of men's coaches were higher when compared to women's coaches. However, this difference was not significant, statistically. In other words, it was determined that the demographic variables which included the gender, marital status, branch and degree major of coaches had no effect on the person-organization fit level. In literature, when

similar studies in which the effects of the demographic specialties on the person-organization fit were examined, the results were encountered which supported the results of the research and in which different findings were obtained. For example, concerning the gender variant, Pekdemir, Koçoğlu, Gürkan, (2013) (Cited by: Sarac 2014: O'Reilly and Dig.) (1991) supported the studies.

Besides this, Uysal-Irak reached a different solution in a research they had made. In this study, it was determined that the person-organization fit average of the women (Ave.=19.31) were higher than the average of the men (Ave.=18.8) (Uysal-Irak, 2014). And Sarris and Kirby, (2005) in their study that they had realized on 117 women-men working in Antarctica between the year of 1950-2000, investigated the effect of the variants of the person-organization fit, gender, age, education, role. The obtained data revealed that in explaining the person-organization fit, the demographic variant which possessed the strongest effect was the gender. The research results remarked that in the Antarctica universe, the person-organization fit perceptions of the men were higher than the women.

As to the marital status, in the study that was made by Pekdemir et al., when the data obtained from the exemplification consisted of 249 persons were examined, a meaningful difference was encountered between the married ones and the single ones in favour of the married participants (Pekdemir, Koçoğlu, Gürkan, 2013).

When the research findings were examined as per the monthly income states which were another independent variant, it was determined that the person-organization fit levels of the coaches revealed a meaningful difference. ($F(2,180)=4,930$; $p>0,05$). It was determined that the coaches whose monthly incomes were above the average had higher person-organization fit level compared to the coaches whose monthly income were lower than the average and the coaches whose monthly income were in the average level. This result was in the quality of supporting the other studies (Oja, Schaeperkoetter, and Clopton, 2015; Knight et al., 2015) which stated that the coaches were attaching importance to the financial issues/supports/contributions.

In the study, according to the correlation results, it was determined that there was a correlation between the intentions of the participants to leave work and the person-organization fit in negative direction and in medium level. ($r=-0,585$; $p<0,05$). In other words, it was determined that as the intentions of the coaches to leave job showed an increase, their organizational fit decreased; as their intentions to leave job showed a decrease, their organizational fit increased. This obtained result was supported by so many studies that were made on the correlation between the person-organization fit and intention to leave job.

When the related studies in literature were scanned, it was revealed for so many times that there was a correlation between the person-organization fit and the intention to leave a job which is important and in the negative direction. Chatman (1991) revealed that the intentions of the workers who perceived the value fit between them and the organization in the lower level were higher compared to the ones who perceived in higher levels. Likewise, Vancouver and Schmitt (1991), Bretz and Judge, (1994), (Khatri, Budhwar and Fern (1999) Westerman and Cyr (2004), McCulloch and Turban (2007), Wheeler et al. (2007), Poyraz and Kama 2008 (Behram and Dinç 2014) reached the solution that there was a strong correlation between the person-organization fit and the intention to leave job. When this finding was evaluated within the framework of the aforesaid hypotheses, it supported the view (Cable and Edwards, 2004) that, in case of the worker's thinking of his not being in compliance with his environment, negative attitudes may occur and by the increase of the compliance level emerged between the person and the organization, the organizations may overcome so many negations. In the researchers that were examined considering this information, it was seen that the person-organization fit was in a parallel correlation with the intention to leave work, however, the effect levels of this correlation were different.

The trained and experienced personnel loss cause important negative results in all sectors. Also, when the trained, qualified personnel loss was examined with regard to the sports club and facilities, this case may cause far greater harms to the organizations. In the light of the data obtained in the study, it can be said that for to reduce the intentions to leave job, the sports organizations should primarily increase the trainer-organization fit.

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